

BIOBUILD

Thermal Solutions for Green Buildings

Deliverable D3.2

Report on selected lignin-based binders (polymerization techniques, properties and processability)

Due Date:	31 December 2025
Submission Date:	27. December 2025
Dissemination level:	PUBLIC
Lead Beneficiary:	BOKU
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Project Acronym: BIOBUILD	Project Number: 101135629
Start Date of Project: 01/01/2024	End Date of Project: 31/12/2027

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Document Control Information	
Title	D3.2 Report on selected lignin-based binders (polymerization techniques, properties and processability)
Editor	Sebastian Gritsch, Sebastian Mayr, Sajjad Ghodrati
Contributors	Sebastian Gritsch, Sebastian Mayr, Sajjad Ghodrati, Meysam Nazari, Nasko Terziev
Reviewer(s)	Sebastian Gritsch, Nasko Terziev
Dissemination Level (please choose just one according to the DoA)	<input type="checkbox"/> SEN - Sensitive (please provide one-page Publishable Summary) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public
Approved by (please tick the boxes after all the partners have provided their written approval of the deliverable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SLU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ASRO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> BOKU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CNR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> COAC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SQIM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pervanovo Invest <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PCMP <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RTDS Association <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UDL <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UNIPD
Underlying IPRs	Are there intellectual property rights included in this deliverable? Yes
Underlying Datasets	Are there relevant datasets included in this deliverable? Yes

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Publishable Summary

Deliverable 3.2 focuses on the development and optimization of enzymatically polymerized lignosulfonates (LS) as sustainable binders for fully bio-based wallboards with enhanced thermal performance and energy storage capabilities. This work supports the BIOBUILD project's goal of advancing circular, low-carbon construction materials that promote energy savings and environmental sustainability in buildings. One of the three bio-binders investigated for wallboard production in the project is lignin.

Lignin is an underutilized by-product of the pulp and paper industry and a promising alternative to conventional fossil-based binders due to its polyaromatic structure. The enzymatic polymerization process reported in this deliverable utilizes laccase enzymes to modify LS under mild conditions. The resulting LS polymers were applied as binders for test panels, which serve as prototypes for the final wallboards, using two production approaches.

Modifying lignosulfonate with vinyl oleate via esterification reduces its hydroxyl group content, as shown by decreased O–H stretching ($\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). This lowers hydrophilicity by replacing polar OH groups with non-polar aliphatic chains from oleate, evidenced by new C–H signals (2923, 2855, 710 cm^{-1}). Consequently, the modified lignosulfonate exhibits improved moisture resistance, with reduced water uptake and better dimensional stability in humid environments compared to unmodified lignosulfonate. The modified material can be polymerized enzymatically applying the same process used for unmodified lignosulfonate.

Cold-pressed composites demonstrated promising mechanical stability and avoided leaching of phase change material (PCM) during production due to the low processing temperature. However, the drying process remains energy-intensive, and the brittleness of dried LS polymers necessitates the use of plasticizers to improve the elasticity and durability of the composites. Among the tested plasticizers, sorbitol emerged as the most promising option due to its biobased origin, cost-effectiveness, and ability to enhance mechanical and hydrophobic properties. Increasing the dry matter content of the binder further improved composite mechanical performance while reducing drying time and energy consumption.

Hot-pressing was identified as a fast and effective production method with the potential to achieve higher mechanical strength and durability. This approach eliminates the need for plasticizers and drying, potentially reducing production costs and aligning with established industrial processes, making it a promising alternative for large-scale applications. However, challenges such as PCM leaching and mat stability need to be addressed to ensure the viability of this process.

Binder stability studies showed that heat inactivation by autoclaving caused severe viscosity loss, led to crumbling boards, and is therefore not recommended. Sodium azide can delay microbial growth in wet binders for up to 3 months. However, due to its toxicity it is unsuitable for scale-up and should be replaced by safer anti-fungal alternatives.

1. Introduction

Deliverable 3.2 “*Report on selected lignin-based binders (polymerization techniques, properties and processability)*” is a part of WP3 “*Upscaling of three bio-binders*”. This deliverable summarizes the activities undertaken in Task 3.2, focusing on the enzymatic polymerization of LS to produce lignin-based binders. It also explores their compatibility with wood particles and fibers, both impregnated and non-impregnated with PCM. Furthermore, the application and processability of various lignin-based binders are reported, with the aim of developing stable composite structures. All outputs were characterized using analytical techniques, including field flow fractionation coupled with multi-angle light scattering (FFF-MALS), mechanical tests, and other methods. The learnings from Task 3.2 provide the basis for production of wallboards with lignin-binder in WP4 and inform WP6’s performance evaluation in energy modelling, LCA and LCC.

The description of Task 3.2, as outlined in the grant agreement, includes the following activities:

- *Functionalization of lignosulfonate with fatty acid vinyl esters prior to enzymatic polymerization.*
- *Compatibility testing of binder recipes (covalently incorporated hydrophobic bio-based molecules binders; binders with bio-based/bio-degradable additives) with wood fibers;*
- *Tuning of binder properties towards stable composite structures and characterization/analysis of polymerization and reaction products: size exclusion chromatography coupled with multi angle light scattering detector (SEC-MALS), photometric assays to determine phenolic content and enzyme activities, rheometry, 1H-NMR, 13C-NMR, 31P-NMR spectra, DSC and TGA analysis and swelling/solubility analyses.*

The work in Deliverable 3.2 was a collaboration between SLU and BOKU. According to the project’s plan, “*SLU functionalized lignosulfonate with fatty acid vinyl esters prior to enzymatic polymerization. BOKU studied the compatibility of binders with wood fibres and perform analytical analyses and characterisation of the lignin-based binder*”.

2. Optimal conditions for polymerization

Lignosulfonate (LS) is an attractive source to replace the commonly used phenol-formaldehyde in binder formulations due to its intrinsic polyaromatic structure. However, due to its impurity, high heterogeneity and low reactivity lignin in general requires some modifications before it can be used in binder applications. Many of these modifications require high temperatures and the use of mostly harmful chemical catalysts. The use of enzymes presents a milder alternative. Therefore, an enzymatic approach for the polymerization of LS was developed. Through oxidation of the phenol structures present in LS, laccase enzymes induce the formation of phenoxy radicals while simultaneously reducing oxygen to water. These radicals can react either amongst each other or with other functional molecules. When the formed radicals react amongst each other the LS molecules become bigger, leading to a gel-like material in the end. The advantage of this modification is that it can be run at moderate conditions, requires oxygen as the only co-substrate and forms water as by-product. The resulting LS polymers gain new properties, such as insolubility in water and other organic compounds or a higher stickiness. These new properties allow the use of the polymerized LS in various applications e.g., as binder in the production of wood composites such as particle boards. The lignosulfonates were received in liquid form from pulp and paper mills in Austria. While the material could be used directly, it was dried in an oven to extend its shelf life.

The reaction was carried out in a 250 mL laboratory bottle containing 200 mL LS solution. The LS was dissolved overnight in water. Before the reaction was started, the dissolved LS solution was set to a pH of 7 with 4 M NaOH. The vessel was continuously mixed at 500 rpm by an overhead stirrer. As stated above, the only co-substrate required for the enzymatic polymerization is oxygen. Thus, following the oxygen content with an optical sensor during the reaction allows for an online monitoring of the reaction progress. The reaction was oxygenated with a flow rate set to 30 mL/min on the flow meter. After the solution was saturated with oxygen, the reaction was started by adding 25 U per gram LS of *Myceliophthora thermophila* laccase (MtL; Novozym 51003 by Novonosis). The temperature of the reaction is kept stable at 30 °C by using a temperature sensor coupled to a heating plate with a feedback loop for temperature regulation (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Set-up of a 200 mL polymerization of lignosulfonate.

To be able to calculate the needed dosage of the MtL enzyme, an ABTS activity assay is done beforehand. Therein the oxidation of 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt (ABTS) to its cation radical by laccase was monitored by following the formation of the resulting oxidation product at 420 nm on an UV/VIS plate reader (Tecan, Infinite M200, Switzerland). The MtL was diluted accordingly in a 0.1 M NaP buffer, pH 7. The reaction was started by mixing 50 μL of a 0.1 M ABTS solution into 170 μL of the diluted enzyme. The color change was followed at 420 nm for a period of 150 s. The activity was expressed in Units (defined as the amount of enzyme necessary to convert 1 μmol substrate per 1 minute).

The growth of the LS polymers, based on the laccase induced formation of the phenol radicals, can be followed by a steady increase in both viscosity and molecular weight.

Monitoring the increase in viscosity is a fast, indirect way to follow the progress of the reaction. The respective sample can be drawn directly during the ongoing reaction and can be therefore seen as a quasi-online measurement. The respective amount of sample (700 μL) was placed on the measuring plate of the Rheometer (MCR 302, Anton Paar, Austria) equipped with a measuring system consisting of a cone plate with a diameter of 50 mm and an angle of 1° (CP50-1). For the measurement a constant shear rate of 200 s^{-1} was applied for 10 s (with measuring points made every second) at a constant temperature (20°C). For data analyses the Anton Paar software RheoCompass 1.24 was used.

The molecular weight distribution of the samples was additionally determined by using the Wyatt Eclipse NEON field flow fractionation (FFF) system (Wyatt Technology, Santa Barbara, CA, USA). The chromatography system was equipped with a quaternary/binary pump, autosampler 1260 series, a diode array detector (DAD), a RI detector system (Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity), and a MALS HELEOS DAWN II detector (Wyatt Technology, Santa Barbara, CA, USA). The FFF was run with the Eclipse long channel with a spacer height of 350 μm and a 10 kDa cellulose membrane. The mobile phase contained 50 mM NaNO_3 with 200 mg/L NaN_3 . The sample injection volume was 50 μL , and the total runtime for one sample was 80 min. The samples were diluted with the mobile phase to a concentration of 4 mg/mL. The internal system calibration of the detector is controlled with BSA and dextran standards from 6 to 600 kDa. For normalization, band broadening, and alignment of the MALS detector, a BSA standard was used. The software used for data acquisition and analysis was ASTRA 8.2 software from Wyatt Technologies.

To identify possible differences in the structural changes occurring during the polymerization An Attenuated total reflective-Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) is done. Therefore, the dried samples were directly applied to the ATR-FTIR device (Spectrum 100, PerkinElmer). The spectrum was recorded in a range

from 4,000 to 650 cm^{-1} with 30 scans and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The spectra were baseline corrected and normalized at the highest peak of the spectrum (about 1025 cm^{-1}).

Many factors are known to affect enzymatic reactions, such as pH, temperature, enzyme load, presence of ions, etc. Thus, to determine the optimal reaction conditions, different reaction parameters were varied to identify the best suited conditions to optimize the enzymatic polymerization reaction [1], [2].

One factor known to have a big impact on enzymatic reactions is presented by temperature. As a rule of thumb, it is known that the activity of an enzyme is doubled with every 10°C in temperature. Another factor, specifically affecting the laccase catalyzed polymerization of LS, is oxygen since it was found to be an important co-factor for this reaction [3].

To investigate these effects closer, a comparison between the polymerization reaction at room temperature (21°C) and elevated temperature (30°C) both supplied with pure oxygen and a comparison between the reaction supplied with pure oxygen and pressurized air, both at 30°C, was done.

It turned out that different temperatures do not have such a big impact on the polymerization reaction as does oxygen source. Only minor differences in viscosity and molecular weight can be observed for the reaction at different temperatures when supplied with pure oxygen. Both samples with pure oxygen show similar trends in viscosity and molecular weight, although the sample run at 30 °C shows slightly higher values. On the other side the sample supplied with pressurized air, although showing a steady increase in both viscosity and molecular weight, nearly needs twice as long to reach similar values than those of the samples supplied with pure oxygen. The observed decreases in molecular weight in the end of the reaction for all samples can be explained by the increasing insolubility of the formed polymers which are then removed by filtration in sample preparation for FFF-analysis (Figure 2a and b). Interestingly, a comparison of the structural changes by ATR-FTIR did not show significant differences between the compared polymerized samples. Even between the unpolymerized sample and the polymerized samples only minor structural changes are identified (Figure 2c). When looking at the oxygen consumption throughout the reaction, the time point of enzyme addition can be clearly seen by the drop in oxygen content. The subsequent plateau phase shows that the MtL enzyme is reacting with the LS molecules consuming of the supplied oxygen. Near to the end of the reaction the oxygen saturation is increasing again. At this point most of the available phenol groups are oxidized and the increasing viscosity hinders both the oxygen dispersion throughout the system and the enzyme interaction with the LS polymers due to steric restrictions. Further, the oxygen level in the sample supplied with pressurized air is very low until the end of the reaction. The observable peaks in the end again are caused due to the solidification of the LS solution (Figure 2d).

With these findings, it can be summarized that the enzymatic polymerization reaction of LS works best at a temperature of 30°C supplied with pure oxygen. However, since pure oxygen is not always available and expensive, supply with pressurized air was found to be a practicable alternative. Although the reaction takes longer to form the final gel-like material, the use of pressurized air presents a cheap alternative to pure oxygen, especially when the duration of the reaction can be neglected.

Figure 2: Effects of temperature and oxygen on the enzymatic polymerization of liginosulfonate. a) Viscosity increase over time, b) increase of molecular weight over time, c) comparison of FT-IR spectra of the polymers, d) oxygen monitoring during the polymerization.

However, one of the drawbacks of the formed LS polymers is that they become brittle upon drying, restricting their use in certain applications, e.g., coatings or adhesives. Therefore, to increase their flexibility, functional molecules can be added during the polymerization reaction, leading to their incorporation into the growing LS polymers and thus effecting their final properties [4]. To this end different substrates with known plasticizing abilities (glycerol, xylitol, sorbitol, etc.) are investigated for their effect on the LS polymers. Plasticizers are low molecular weight, high boiling point compounds used to increase processability, fluidity, flexibility, and durability of polymers. Commonly applied plasticizers such as phthalates, carbonates, phosphates, etc., possess serious drawbacks such as toxicity or even carcinogenicity and are partly already banned. Accordingly, biobased plasticizers, for instance vegetable oils, polyols, organic acids or fatty acids, are preferably used.

Thus, the plasticizing molecules used were chosen on the basis that they originate from wood processing side streams too, making them biobased (levulinic acid, glycerol, xylitol, sorbitol). However, despite being not biobased but presenting a commonly used industrial plasticizer, polyethylene glycol (PEG-600 and PEG-1000) was also investigated.

To investigate the effects of the plasticizers added on the resulting LS polymers the resulting gel-like material is cast into films, allowing determination of water contact angle and tensile strength. Both metrics are important properties for binder applications. The water contact angle is a possibility to determine the hydrophobicity of a surface, being hydrophobic is important for binders since they should not dissolve when encountering water. A material is defined to be hydrophobic when the contact angle is above 90°. For the measurement a drop shape analyzer device (DSA100, Krüss, Germany) was used. Thereby, a picture is taken when a drop of water is deposited on the surface of the sample allowing determination of the contact angle between the drop and the

sample. To this end, the DSA 4.0 software by Krüss was used. Half of the investigated plasticizers (levulinic acid, PEG-1000 and xylitol) had contact angles above 90°, while the remaining ones (glycerol, PEG-600 and sorbitol) were below 90°, with the lowest contact angle found for glycerol.

A high tensile strength of a binder is important for the durability of the final particle board. Therefore, the investigated formulations were investigated regarding their stability on a universal testing machine (BZ1-EXFR002, Zwick/Roell). Considering tensile strength, the best result was obtained for xylitol, followed by glycerol and sorbitol. Low tensile strength was found for levulinic acid and PEG-600.

Based on these findings the formulation containing xylitol seems to be the best option to be used as plasticizer for the formulation of the LS binder, since it showed both the highest contact angle and tensile strength (Figure 3).

Anyhow, these results apply only for the LS binder itself. When integrated in composites, the interaction of the binder with wood particles and PCM could affect the properties of the final board, thus this needs to be investigated further.

Figure 3: Tensile strength and water contact angle of lignin binders containing different plasticizers.

3. Functionalization of liginosulfonates with fatty acid vinyl esters

3.1 Synthesis of vinyl ester of oleic acid

One of the objectives in Task 3.2 was to convert liginosulfonates to more hydrophobic and “vinyl-reactive” substrate, to ensure better co-polymerization with fatty chains during the subsequent enzymatic step. Functionalization with fatty acid vinyl esters means grafting of aliphatic fatty chains onto the phenolic or aliphatic hydroxyl groups of liginosulfonates via an ester linkage, using the vinyl ester as an acyl donor. The above is designed to reduce polarity and increase hydrophobicity of the modified liginosulfonates.

By pre-installing fatty chains, the enzymatic polymerization (typically laccase-mediated via phenoxy radicals) proceeds on a liginosulfonate substrate that already carries hydrophobic side groups, the resulting polymer network combines aromatic lignin domains with flexible fatty moieties. This strategy was proposed to improve the moisture resistance of the modified liginosulfonates.

For synthesis of vinyl ester of oleic acid (vinyl oleate), a similar approach as in [5] was adopted with some modifications. For this purpose, 10.56 g of oleic acid was charged into a three-neck round-bottom flask equipped with a reflux condenser. Subsequently, 20 mL of dimethylformamide (DMF) was added as solvent, and the mixture was stirred for 15 min (Figure 4). In the next step, 32.2 g of vinyl acetate (10 equivalents in excess relative to oleic acid) was added. Catalyst HS157 and sodium acetate were then added to adjust and control the pH of the solution. The reaction mixture was maintained at 110°C in an oil bath and continuously stirred at

this temperature for 24 h under a continuous argon purge. The chemical reaction in this step is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the synthesis setup and photo picture of the experimental setup.

Figure 5: Reagents and raw materials used for synthesis of vinyl oleate (above) and chemical reaction between oleic acid and vinyl acetate leading to formation of vinyl oleate (below).

For separation of vinyl oleate, 85 mL of hexane was added to the reaction mixture, where phase separation occurred rapidly. Since vinyl oleate is mostly nonpolar, while vinyl acetate and DMF are polar, it is assumed that the product is present in the hexane phase while the unreacted vinyl acetate remains within DMF phase. The hexane phase was washed four times with 85 mL of distilled water to ensure that no vinyl acetate remained in the hexane phase. Figure 6 shows hexane and aqueous phases during the separation process of vinyl oleate.

Figure 6: Phase separation during vinyl oleate purification: the hexane phase is on top while the DMF/water phase is below.

Considering the molar masses of oleic acid (282.46 g/mol) and vinyl oleate (308.46 g/mol), the amount of oleic acid used (10.56 g) and the mass of vinyl oleate obtained (11.00 g), the *reaction yield* was 95%.

For the characterization of vinyl oleate and its comparison with oleic acid, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis was conducted in the range of 4000–450 cm^{-1} . The results are presented in Figure 7. A broad O–H stretching in the oleic acid spectrum, which begins at around 3400 cm^{-1} and overlaps with the CH_2 stretching region, is not present in the vinyl oleate spectrum. This disappearance indicates the consumption of hydroxyl groups and the formation of vinyl ester groups.

The strong peaks corresponding to asymmetric CH_2 stretching at approximately 2923 cm^{-1} and symmetric CH_2 stretching at around 2854 cm^{-1} remain unchanged since the aliphatic chain of oleic acid does not undergo structural modification during esterification.

The intense C=O stretching peak of oleic acid at around 1708 cm^{-1} shifts to 1758 cm^{-1} in vinyl oleate, confirming the formation of the vinyl ester. The peak at approximately 1284 cm^{-1} , attributed to the C–O single bond in the carboxyl group of oleic acid, is absent in the vinyl oleate spectrum, indicating the complete conversion of the hydroxyl-containing carboxyl group. In contrast, a strong peak at 1142 cm^{-1} , associated with C–O stretching of the ester linkage, appears clearly in vinyl oleate and is not present in oleic acid.

The C=C stretching peak at 1647 cm^{-1} observed in vinyl oleate but absent in the oleic acid spectrum, provides additional evidence of successful vinyl ester formation; the above is in accordance with previous studies [10–13].

Figure 7: FTIR spectra of oleic acid and the synthesized vinyl oleate.

3.2 Grafting of oleate ester onto lignosulfonate

For grafting of the oleate ester onto lignosulfonate, 20 g of lignosulfonate was dissolved in 50 mL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). A setup identical to that used in the previous reaction was employed; the only difference was that the reaction was carried out under a nitrogen atmosphere instead of argon. Dissolution was performed at 80°C for 30 min with magnetic stirring. In the next step, 11 g of vinyl oleate was mixed with 40 mL of DMSO and then added to the lignosulfonate solution. Considering that lignosulfonate contains approximately 1 mmol/g of phenolic hydroxyl groups [6, 7], a stoichiometric amount of catalyst (2,6-lutidine), 2.14 g corresponding to one equivalent relative to the phenolic hydroxyl groups, was added to the flask. The temperature was then raised to 110°C and maintained for 24 h. The reaction scheme and the structure of catalysts are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Chemical reaction between lignosulfonate and vinyl oleate and a simplified chemical structure of lignosulfonate (in blue) according to [8, 9]. 2,6-lutidine and its chemical structure.

The reaction mixture was cooled, and the polymeric fraction was precipitated in acetone. The acetone was chosen because the oleate ester of lignosulfonate is insoluble in it, while any unreacted vinyl oleate, catalyst, and DMSO are soluble. The reaction mixture was slowly added to 1000 mL of acetone while stirring with a magnetic stirrer. The addition required approximately 20 min, after which stirring was continued for an additional 10 min. The stirring stopped, and the mixture left to settle for sedimentation (Figure 9a). The acetone phase was subsequently removed, and the polymeric material was washed with 100 mL of acetone two more times. The final product was dried at 60°C for 24 h (Figure 9b).

Figure 9: Phase separation during purification of esterified lignosulfonate with the acetone phase is on top and sedimented polymer underneath (a); the modified lignosulfonate (b).

FTIR results for lignosulfonate and modified lignosulfonate are presented in Figure 10. The broad peak at around 3300 cm^{-1} , corresponding to O–H stretching of both phenolic and aliphatic groups, is visible in both lignosulfonate and modified lignosulfonate. However, its lower intensity in the modified sample indicates that part of the hydroxyl groups reacted with vinyl oleate.

The peaks associated with C–H stretching of methylene groups at 2923 cm^{-1} and 2855 cm^{-1} are more intense in the modified lignosulfonate, further supporting the introduction of the long aliphatic chain from vinyl oleate into the lignosulfonate structure.

The ester linkage peak at 1143 cm^{-1} is also more intense in the modified lignosulfonate than in the unmodified sample, indicating successful formation of ester bonds during the reaction. The peak at 950 cm^{-1} , attributed to the ester linkage, appears in the modified lignosulfonate but is absent in the unmodified version.

The C–H rocking vibration peak of the aliphatic chain of the oleate group at 710 cm^{-1} is present in the modified lignosulfonate but not in the unmodified sample, providing additional confirmation of successful grafting [10-13]. It is concluded that modification of lignosulfonate with vinyl oleate led to decreased O–H stretching intensity (around 3300 cm^{-1}), indicating hydroxyl group reaction. Increased C–H stretching peaks (2923 cm^{-1} and 2855 cm^{-1}) and stronger ester peaks (1143 cm^{-1} and 950 cm^{-1}) confirm successful ester bond formation. The new C–H rocking vibration at 710 cm^{-1} further evidence grafting of the long aliphatic oleate chain onto lignosulfonate. The modified lignosulfonate is more hydrophobic than the initial lignosulfonate due to the above chemical modification.

Figure 10: FTIR spectra of lignosulfonate and modified lignosulfonate.

3.3 Polymerization of functionalized Lignosulfonate

A small scale polymerization trial was performed with the functionalized lignosulfonate. Therefore 15 mL of a 10% (w/w) solution were prepared by dissolving 1.5 g functionalized lignosulfonate in 13.5 mL water and adjusting the pH to 7.0 with 1 M NaOH. Despite being functionalized with fatty acid esters, the lignosulfonate remained soluble in water. The reaction was performed in a 30 mL glass vial agitated by magnetic stirrer at 500 rpm and room temperature. The liquid was sparged with oxygen at 30 mL/min. 25 U/g lignin were added once the solution was saturated with oxygen, to start the reaction. Viscosity and molecular weight were monitored as described in chapter 0.

Right after the initial enzyme addition, the oxygen level dropped, indicating the enzyme's ability to oxidize the modified lignosulfonate molecules. Shortly afterwards, the oxygen content began to rise back to its original level (Figure 11b). As the viscosity did not increase as expected from the polymerization of unmodified lignosulfonate (see Figure 2c), only displaying a slight increase from 2.6 mPas to 4.8 mPas, and of fear, that solvent residues from functionalization might have harmed the enzyme, a second dose of enzyme was added after 6 h and the polymerization was continued overnight. This time no drop in oxygen content was observed, suggesting that indeed all molecules had already been oxidized. The next day a gel had formed, indicating a successful polymerization of the functionalized lignosulfonate. The drop in oxygen content suggests, the polymerization was finished after approximately 18 h, which is a significant increase compared to unmodified LS which finished after 2.5 h.

Interestingly the molecular weight displayed a stark increase in the first 6 h reaching up to 106 kDa, and was significantly higher than polymerized unmodified LS (Figure 11a). As before, the drop in molecular weight at the last time point is due to the decreased solubility of the large molecules. The large increase in molecular weight and low increase in viscosity suggests that the structural changes during functionalization favored the formation of larger, more linear polymer chains, instead of intermolecular cross-linking. This can be explained by the fact that the functionalized lignosulfonate molecules possess fewer hydroxyl groups, which could cross-link, as the positions are blocked by oleic acid esters.

Figure 11: Polymerization of functionalized lignosulfonate where a) molecular weight (kDa) and viscosity (mPas) increase over time and b) oxygen monitoring during the polymerization. The orange arrows indicate the time points of enzyme addition.

These small-scale experiments were not intended to yield material for tests with lignin-binder for composite production. However, the tests showed that functionalization of lignosulfonate is possible, and the material can still be polymerized enzymatically applying the same processes used for unmodified lignosulfonate.

The suggested method can be implemented further in the work of WP4 and specifically in Deliverables D4.2 “Demonstration of lignin binder production” and D4.3 “Demonstration of wallboard production (epoxy oil and lignin as binder)”. The synthesis of modified lignosulfonates is a demonstration, and its applicability depends on the findings in D4.5 “Report on bio-composite mechanical and physical properties”, D4.6 “Report on VOCs emissions from bio-composites” and D4.7 “Report on the overall performance of produced flooring and wallboards”.

4. Binder application in wood composites

The wood particles and fibers used in T3.2, both impregnated with EP and non-impregnated, were provided by SLU. Impregnation was performed in WP2 following the optimized procedure reported in D2.2. The compatibility of the lignin binders with wood fibers and particles, both impregnated with PCM and non-impregnated, was tested. Therefore, the binders were tested both in their wet form, after polymerization, and dried, for better control over the water content in the mats.

4.1 Cold pressing

During the production of conventional particle boards, the binder is sprayed onto the wood particles for an even distribution. Due to the high viscosity of lignin binders this is not possible. Instead, the wet lignin binders were mixed with the wood particles for 30 min in a mixer to ensure the particles are coated uniformly. The mixture was then transferred into a 25 cm x 25 cm mold and pressed in a hydraulic press for 10 min at 30 – 40 bar and 10°C. Pressing at low temperatures ensured the PCM would not melt but stay in the composite. The mold containing the pressed mat was then transferred into an oven and dried for 24 h at 70°C. To minimize deformation, the lid was kept on during the first 5 h of drying.

Composites with wood fibers instead of particles were prepared using the same process. Fiber-based composites displayed higher bending strength (up to 3 MPa) compared to particle-based composites, indicating that fibers could yield stronger materials. However, the lack of proper equipment for processing fibers at our department led to uneven binder distribution, as the fibers immediately absorbed the binder, forming lumps (see Figure 12). Therefore, further experiments were conducted mainly with wood particles.

Figure 12: Composite composed of pine wood fibers, pine fibres impregnated with PCM and lignin binder. Dark brown lignin spots are visible in the fiberboard due to improper mixing.

The composites were tested for bending strength and swelling at our institute using standardized methods, EN 310:1993 [14] and EN 317:1993 [15], respectively. Due to the small size of the composites, sample dimensions for both tests were adjusted and deviated from the standards outlined in the norms. For bending strength tests, the sample dimensions were modified to 2 cm × 20 cm, while for swelling tests, the dimensions were adjusted to 3 cm × 3 cm. These tests allowed for screening of promising recipes. Selected samples were subsequently sent to project partners for more comprehensive testing as part of Work Package 4 activities. A list of composites produced from different lignin binders is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Composite formulations tested with different lignin binders and wood types. The lignin binders vary in plasticizer type, as well as lignin and plasticizer content. The table outlines the composition percentages and densities of the resulting composites.

Label	Wood type	Wood Particles + PCM	Wood particles	Binder in dry composite	Lignin in binder	Plasticizer in binder	Plasticizer	Density
		% w/w	% w/w	% w/w	% w/w	% w/w		kg/m ³
PEG-01-30	Pine	40	30	30	20	10	PEG600	485.0
LA-01-30	Pine	40	30	30	20	8.3	Levulinic acid	396.7
G-01-15	Pine	50	35	15	20	10	Glycerol	418.2
G-01-26	Pine	43	30	26	20	10	Glycerol	NA
X-01-15	Pine	50	35	15	20	16.6	Xylitol	396.7
X-01-26	Pine	43	30	26	20	16.6	Xylitol	447.6
S-01-15	Pine	50	35	15	20	16.6	Sorbitol	398.2
S-01-26	Pine	43	30	26	20	16.6	Sorbitol	472.8
S-01-35	Pine	35	30	35	20	16.6	Sorbitol	418.7
S-01-30	Pine	40	30	30	20	16.6	Sorbitol	515.8
S-03-30	Pine	40	30	30	20	10	Sorbitol	456.5
S-04-30	Poplar	40	30	30	20	16.6	Sorbitol	502.2

S-05-30	Birch	40	30	30	20	16.6	Sorbitol	565.6
S-06-30	Pine	40	30	30	27	22.4	Sorbitol	555.9
S-07-30	Pine	40	25 + 5 fibers	30	20	16.6	Sorbitol	521.2

Interestingly, using xylitol and glycerol as plasticizer resulted in weaker composite bonding compared to sorbitol, even though they showed similar (glycerol) or even higher (xylitol) strength when testing the binder materials themselves (Figure 14). Addition of 8% levulinic acid both lead to relatively weak tensile strength in the binder and poor performance of the resulting composite. Among the tested plasticizers, PEG600 showed relatively good mechanical strength, slightly higher than S-01-30, which was used during the demonstration reported in D4.3. However, sorbitol was preferred as the plasticizer of choice due to its lower market price (550 – 700 USD/MT [16] compared to 1070 USD/MT for PEG600 [17]) and its biological origin. While PEG600 is biodegradable, it is not biobased, making sorbitol a more sustainable option as it is both biobased and biodegradable and therefore better aligns with the goal of developing environmentally friendly bio-composites.

Figure 13: Composites composed of Scots pine unimpregnated particles, particles impregnated with PCM and lignin binder with sorbitol. Left: 15% lignin binder, right: 30% lignin binder.

Testing these initial cold-pressed composites revealed that a higher binder content (30% or 35% in S-01-30 and S-01-35) had a darker color (Figure 13) and resulted in greater mechanical stability compared to panels with lower binder content (S-01-15 and S-01-26; see Figure 14). In such cases the binder creates a matrix in which the wood particles are embedded, making the strength of the binder itself a critical factor.

S-01-30 showed promising results and was chosen for the demonstration reported in D4.3 “*Demonstration of wallboard production (epoxy & lignin as binders)*”, which was performed in May 2025 at Pervanovo facilities in Viken, Sweden. One key learning was that the moisture content of the lignin wallboards should be reduced to decrease the drying time. Based on these requirements tests with increased dry matter were conducted. A binder with the same ratio of lignin to plasticizer as used in S-01-30 was prepared having 50% total dry matter. Despite the high viscosity the binder could still be mixed with the wood particles resulting in uniformly coated particles. The resulting composite (S-06-30) displayed higher bending strength compared to higher water content boards.

This implies that the removal of high amounts of water during the drying process weakens the bond. The shrinking of binder during the drying process could leave cavities in the composite which may lead to the lower bending strength. This shrinkage is also visible in the dried composites which have an uneven and rough surface.

Figure 14: Bending strength and swelling of wood particle composites with lignin-based binders. High values in bending strength and low values in swelling are advantageous.

While the swelling thickness after 24 h seems to vary greatly even in similar compositions (Figure 14), they mostly comply with the standards for non-load-bearing boards for use in humid conditions which have a limit of 17 % for boards of similar thickness. Although swelling is not critical for the planned application of the composites, it is noteworthy that the boards still meet these standards, demonstrating their potential for broader applications.

The cold-pressing process used for these composites proved to be energy-efficient compared to hot-pressing and ensured that no PCM was leached from the impregnated particles during production. Stable composites could be produced using this method, and birch and poplar yielded similar results to pine when the same binder was used indicating that the type of wood does not affect the properties of composites produced in this process. However, the strength of the composites is still significantly lower than the standards for non-load-bearing particle boards according to EN 312:2010, which require a bending strength of 10.5 N/mm² for boards of similar thickness. Additionally, the drying process remains energy-intensive due to the high moisture content of the binder, which must be removed before the panels can be used.

4.2 Hot pressing

During hot-pressing in conventional particle boards, the formaldehyde resins chemically cross-link, and excess water evaporates. The pressing process usually only lasts a few minutes with no further curing steps needed [18]. To address the long drying times of cold-pressed composites and align with established industrial processes, the hot pressing of particle boards with lignin-based binders was investigated as an alternative.

The low bending strength of the cold-pressed composites is likely due to the limited chemical interactions between the binder and the wood, as the pressing temperature was kept low to preserve the PCM. Hot pressing at higher temperatures is known to promote cross-linking between lignin [19], which could improve bonding strength between binder and wood particles. But this process presents other challenges.

One consideration is the moisture content of the mat during hot pressing. Excess water can lead to blowouts during pressing, making precise control of the water content essential. Therefore, lignin binders with low water content are preferred.

Another challenge is the inclusion of PCM in the composites. The PCM is a vital component in the composites but pressing at high temperatures risks losing it through leaching. Strategies to prevent the loss of PCM include mixing impregnated with unimpregnated particles or producing 3-layer boards with surface layers composed of unimpregnated particles, while the PCM-impregnated particles are in the core layer. This way the liquid PCM could be absorbed by unimpregnated particles.

Since the bonding mechanism in hot pressing differs fundamentally from that in cold pressing, initial experiments were conducted using polymerized lignin as a binder without the addition of plasticizers. Two options consisting

of wet binder, used directly after polymerization, and dried binder powder were tested. Applying dried binder has the advantage that the water content can be controlled precisely. Additionally, it has a higher shelf life, is easier to transport, and could reduce shipping costs.

Currently, only small-scale tests have been conducted (Figure 15). One of the main challenges is achieving proper dispersion of lignin binder powder without adding excessive water. To address this, different wetting agents were tested to ensure uniform distribution of the binder within the mat. Wood particles were mixed with 5% (per weight of wood) dry lignin binder and defined amounts of wetting agents to adjust the moisture content and ensure binder adherence to the wood particles. Impregnated particles did not have this issue, as the oily PCM film around the particles facilitates lignin powder adherence. However, mat stability at the targeted moisture content remains an issue that needs to be resolved. The mixtures were then pressed at 190 °C for several min without using a mold. The resulting boards exhibited looseness at the edges, suggesting that mat stability needs to be improved to ensure uniform compaction during hot pressing.

Figure 15: Test pieces hot-pressed with lignin binder: a) Pine particles with wet lignin binder (20 % dry substance) b) Pine particles with powdered lignin binder, c) Mix of impregnated and unimpregnated pine particles with powdered lignin binder, d) Impregnated pine particles with powdered lignin binder

Despite these challenges, initial results suggest that hot pressing wood particles with lignin-based binders could be a promising approach. Although no mechanical tests were performed due to the small sample size of the initial tests, the hot-pressed boards appeared significantly stronger than cold-pressed panels. The density of these test pieces was in the range of 700 – 950 kg/m³. Additionally, the surface of the hot-pressed panels was smooth, in contrast to the rough surface of cold-pressed composites, which is another advantage of this method, as it reduces the need of sanding for a smooth finish in the final product.

5. Binder stability

Because reactive lignin species remain in the binder after aeration stops, polymerization can continue, leading to further crosslinking and viscosity increase. Additionally, it was observed that the binder has limited shelf life due to microbial growth, even when stored at 4 °C. To address these points two approaches were considered: heat inactivation and chemical stabilization.

For heat inactivation, the sorbitol containing binder was produced as described above. Once the binder reached a viscosity of 1888 mPas, the bottle was heated in an autoclave to 121 °C and the temperature was maintained for 20 min. Autoclaving greatly reduced the binder's viscosity to 96 mPas. The binder was used to produce a composite. Since the binder was too liquid, it leached during the pressing process. The resulting composite after drying was very fragile and crumbled when moved (Figure 16). Autoclaving therefore is not a suggested treatment for wet binders.

Figure 16: Composite prepared with heat-inactivated lignin binder. The board is very fragile and crumbles easily.

To test the second approach, chemical stabilization, a batch of binder was prepared as described above. The polymerization was stopped earlier to investigate the effects of chemical stabilization on the polymerization progress. The batch was split in two parts. One part stored without further treatment in an airtight bottle at room temperature, while the other was supplemented with 200 ppm NaN_3 before being stored. While both batches developed a skin on the surface, the batch treated with azide remained less viscous (550 mPas) than the untreated control (1000 mPas) after 2 weeks of storage. The control started to grow mold after two weeks, while the treated batch started to show microbial growth after 3 months.

Since the high dry-matter binders tested in section 4.1, displaying a very high viscosity, were still processable it seems unnecessary to stop the polymerization for binder production. Hence the only point to consider is the shelf life of the binder. Microbial growth can effectively be delayed by addition of NaN_3 . But due to its high toxicity, this is not advised in large scale production. Safer methods might include addition potassium sorbate and or other food grade preservatives [20], [21], [22]. Using dried lignin binder largely resolves these issues. In the dry state, microbial growth is suppressed and shelf life and logistics are improved as no cooling is needed for storage.

6. Conclusion

Deliverable 3.2 has demonstrated the feasibility of using enzymatic polymerized LS for binder applications, offering a sustainable alternative to conventional formaldehyde-based binders. The enzymatic approach, utilizing laccase enzymes, is effective under moderate conditions, requiring only oxygen as a co-substrate and producing water as the sole by-product. Stable composites containing wood particles of different wood types and wood particles impregnated with PCM could be produced using two different approaches.

Modifying lignosulfonate with vinyl oleate via esterification reduces its hydroxyl group content, as shown by decreased O–H stretching ($\sim 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). This lowers hydrophilicity by replacing polar OH groups with non-polar aliphatic chains from oleate, evidenced by new C–H signals ($2923, 2855, 710 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Consequently, the modified lignosulfonate exhibits improved moisture resistance, with reduced water uptake and better dimensional stability in humid environments compared to unmodified lignosulfonate. The modified material was polymerized enzymatically applying the same process used for unmodified lignosulfonate.

Cold-pressed composites avoid PCM leaching during pressing due to the low temperature. However, due to the brittleness of dried LS polymers plasticizers are needed to improve flexibility and durability of the binder. Among the tested plasticizers, sorbitol emerged as the most promising option due to its biobased origin, cost-

effectiveness, and ability to enhance both tensile strength and water contact angle. While polyethylene glycol (PEG600) showed comparable mechanical performance, its higher cost and non-biobased nature make sorbitol a more sustainable choice for future applications. Panels produced this way demonstrated promising mechanical stability. However, the drying process remains energy-intensive due to high water content of the binder, which also contributes to shrinkage and uneven surface textures. Increasing the dry matter of the binder significantly increased the mechanical strength of the composite. These findings suggest that optimizing the dry matter content of the binder could both increase the composite performance and reduce the drying time and therefore energy consumption.

Hot-pressed composites showed potential for achieving higher mechanical strength compared to cold-pressed panels, likely due to the enhanced chemical interactions between lignin and wood particles at elevated temperatures. Due to this chemical cross-linking, this approach manages without the need of plasticizers, which could save production costs of lignin-binders. However, challenges such as PCM leaching and mat stability need to be addressed to ensure the viability of this process. Strategies like optimizing the pressing parameters, using layered structures or a higher share of unimpregnated particles could mitigate PCM loss during hot pressing. Additionally, using dried binder would also resolve binder stability issues, like microbial growth and energy demand for cold storage.

The primary binder stability concern is the shelf life of wet binders. Autoclave heat inactivation caused severe viscosity loss and poor panel performance and is therefore not recommended. Sodium azide addition delays microbial growth but is unsuitable for scale-up due to its toxicity. Instead, food-grade antifungals (e.g., potassium sorbate) should be considered to produce wet binder formulations.

Two lignin-binder formulations are selected for consideration in wallboard production: the sorbitol containing wet binder (S-06) for cold-pressed panels, which performed best among the wet binders, and a dry polymerized lignin binder for hot-pressing. While recipes for hot-pressing will be further tuned to improve powder dispersion and mitigate PCM leaching, the process remains promising for the fast and efficient production of wallboards, while aligning with already established industrial processes.

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